

Geospatial Analysis of Road Traffic Accident Hotspot along Gadar Kafin Gana to Birnin Kudu Expressway Jigawa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study analyzes the accident trends from 2010 to 2022 and moves on to locate and map out accident hotspots along Gadar Kafin Gana to Birnin Kudu Expressway in Jigawa State Nigeria. The FRSC records and Global Positioning Systems (GPS) provided the data used in this study. Though, tables, percentages, ArcGIS 10.1 Kernel Density Estimation (KDE), and the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) were the tools used for analysis. Sadly, the study found that the highest frequency of fatality was 58.3% recorded in 2013 which was closely followed by 47.1%, 46.7%, and 46.2% in 2020, 2019, and 2022 respectively. The greatest percentage of people with serious injuries was 31.3% in 2021, followed by 28.5% in 2018. However, the largest percentage of minor injuries 58.3% was recorded in 2017. The study further revealed that there was a decline in the number of accident cases, but there was an increase in the fatality rate whenever an accident occurs in the study area. The study also identified seventeen (17) accident hotspot locations in the study area. It was also discovered that Kantoga Village, with a value of 16.95, had the highest Accident Point Weighting, followed closely by Alu Agro Farm and Kafin Gana Bridge, with values of 15.45 and 11.85, respectively. Additionally, it was discovered that the accident hotspots were not evenly distributed along the road. It was recommended that a major factor in encouraging excellent traffic rule compliance is enhanced road users' awareness of the risks linked to traveling at high speeds on roads with sharp bends, narrow bridges, and potholes.

Keywords: Geospatial Analysis, Casualty, Hotspot, Kernel Density Estimation and Analytical Hierarchy Process

1.0 Introduction

Every nation's ability to grow economically depends on its transportation infrastructure, which includes air, rail, and road links, with roads being the most important for moving both goods and individuals. A strong road system is essential because it connects rural and urban areas. Therefore, it is vital to point out that road safety is a crucial factor since it is essential to a successful road transport growth strategy in nations (Jobin 2015). Among the three modes of transportation air,

land, and water road accidents are the most common because land is different from the other two in many ways. It is the only mean that is easily accessible and close to a lot of people. In a way, it is less expensive. Transport by road is projected to be used by around 90% of people and 75% of goods and services are being transported. Furthermore, road transport is very essential in both the settings of rural and urban societies, this is because of its importance to economic success and general well-being. The growth in the population of cities, road transport systems, and travel distances has brought about adverse effects like traffic jams, air, environmental and noise pollution as well as car accidents.

An accident is an unpleasant damage that happens unexpectedly and without warning. Road, human, vehicle, and environmental factors all contribute to an accident before, during, and after it occurs, threatening family safety (Oyedepo and Makinde, 2010). A number of countries are experiencing significant transport-related problems as a result of the rising demand for transport globally. At this time, effective, safe, practical, and faster modes of transport need to be developed (Apparao, Mallikarjunareddy, and Raju 2013). Consequently, the road transport system is one of the biggest mobility risk systems that people must deal with on a daily basis. Road Traffic Accidents are increasing as a result of the transport infrastructure system's slower growth rate when compared to other sectors, such as real estate and industrial zones. Low- and middle-income countries with inadequate transportation infrastructure, such as Nigeria, account for about one-third of fatalities involving cars, bikes, and pedestrians (WHO 2015).

One of the biggest problems in the world is traffic accidents, which have significant effects on society, the economy, and politics. The increasing number of traffic accidents has a negative influence on socioeconomic development, sustainability, and road safety (Wijnen, 2021). On the other hand, around 1.3 million individuals usually get involved in traffic accidents each year 90% of the deaths occurred in low- and middle-income nations (WHO 2019). The World Health Organization (2017a) predicts that by 2030, RTAs will be accountable for more fatalities and disability-adjusted life years lost than HIV/AIDS, malaria, cerebrovascular disease, and tuberculosis put together. In light of its negative effects on the economy and health, which are shown by high rates of disease and mortality, RTA has ultimately contributed to a worldwide burden (World Health Organization, 2017b). Additionally, by 2030, it is expected to rank as the fourth most common cause of lost disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) (Alam and Mahal, 2016). With the development of road safety analysis, local governments can now implement the best policies to reduce the number of accidents on the roads (Li, Xie, and Shu, 2021; Tola, Demissie, Saathoff, Gebissa, 2021). Though, according to the International Transport Forum (2017), traffic accidents globally result in about 50 million injuries and over one million fatality cases yearly. While the degree varies from country to country, poor countries are the hardest hit. The loss of life, destruction of property, and pain it causes in people's minds are severe.

It has been estimated in developing nations that traffic accidents cost over \$100 billion a year, or \$51 billion globally (National Highway Traffic Safety Administration, 2022). While, in Nigeria the road accidents are estimated to cost about 80 billion Naira each year (CBN 2020). On the other hand, In low-income nations, RTAs are believed to make about 1% of GDP. In a middle-income country, it is expected to be 1.5% of GNP, while in a high-income country, it is 2%. The lower and middle-income nations' total income of \$65 billion exceeds the amount of aid they receive. Nigeria, along with Ethiopia, South Africa, and Sudan, accounts for half of all road fatalities and injuries in sub-Saharan Africa, having the highest road injury fatality rate (52.4 per 100,000 people) in the entire world.

According to Dereli and Erdogan (2017) identifying the exact place where and when accidents frequently occur is crucial in lowering the occurrence of accidents. Places on a highway that have a higher accident rate are referred to as hot spots or "black spots". The word "hotspot" describes a section of road that is considered to be a high-risk area for car crashes. Erdogan, Yilmaz, Baybura, and Gullu (2008) stated that in Turkey a location that an accident occurs four times in a year is considered as a black spot or hotspot. Thus, a road location experiencing a high number of accidents, when compared to other locations, is classified as a "hot spot" or "black spot". This is in accordance with the following; Dereli, and Erdogan (2017); Ryder, Gahr, Dahlinger (2016); W/Yohannes, and Minale (2015); Thakali, Kwon, and Fu (2015); and Cheng, Gill, Zhang, Vo, Wen, and Li (2020); as well as Feng, Wang, Lee, Abdel-Aty, and Mao (2020). Results of some related research indicate that RTA incidents are not sporadic in both space and time. Xia and Yan (2008) further affirmed that these locations are actually distinguished by a number of crucial elements such as geometric layout, traffic volume, the surrounding area, extreme weather, etc. It is extremely important to identify likely risky places related to accident occurrence time (Harirforoush 2017) in order to properly design accident prevention plans.

The first stage in any highway safety management process is to identify the accident-prone locations. According to Thakali, Kwon, and Fu (2015); and Feng, Wang, Lee, Abdel-Aty, and Mao (2020), the systematic approach of road accident hotspot identification is another term for finding road segments with a high accident risk that exceeds the usual limit of road safety. The GIS program, which has a vast geographical database, can be used to identify hotspots. It can perform geographic analysis (spatial grouping) on road accidents and visualize accident locations (mapping), as asserted by (Vemulapalli, Ulak, Ozguven, Sando, Horner, Abdelrazig, and Moses (2017); Saha, Alluri, Gan, and Wu (2018); Srikanth, Srikanth, and Arockiasamy, (2019); Hashtarkhani, Kiani, Bergquist, Bagheri, VafaeiNejad, and Tara, (2020); Nazneen, Rezapour, and Ksaibati, (2020) in similar studies they all conducted.

A vital transport route linking several North Eastern states of Nigeria to the busy commercial center of Kano in the North West is the Gadar Kafin Gana-Birnin Kudu expressway in Jigawa state. This strategic route has experienced a noticeable increase in traffic, which is mostly due to Jigawa state's booming economic activities. Unfortunately, the increased level of traffic has resulted in a rise in traffic accidents along this route. Looking at the route key importance to the economic, social and political landscape to the entire country, it is essential to identify accident-prone locations along this corridor.

To address this challenge, the study achieved the following objectives. One, is to analyze the patterns of traffic accidents in the study area from 2010-2022. Two, is to identify and carefully map out the precise hotspot with higher chances of accidents along the study route. This study is structured into five sections for the sake of order and clarity. The first section consists of an overview of the study context and the objective. In the second section reviewed literature on road crashes and hotspots. The third section goes into detail on the methodology employed to conduct the study. Subsequently, the fourth section discussed the result and major findings. The conclusion and recommendations are found in the fifth and final section of the paper.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Risk Theory

According to Sjorberg and Biel (1983), Rundmo and Iversen (2004), and Moen and Rundmo (2005), risk is the subjective assessment of the likelihood that a specific negative event will occur and the degree to which the individual is concerned about the consequences of this event. As a result, the combination of perceived probability and severity of consequences affects

how an individual perceives risk. Dejoy (1989) stated that risk in traffic accidents depends on four factors. The first is exposure, which refers to how much various users or a particular population density move around or transits inside the system. The second factor is the crash probability at any given exposure. The possibility of injuries given a crash is the third factor. The result of an injury is the fourth component. Human mistake, kinetic energy, human body tolerance, and post-crash care can all be used to explain risk (Bastide, Moatti, Pages, and Fagan 1989).

2.1.1 Road Traffic Accidents

Road accidents are not only a random occurrence they are caused, given that Nigeria has the greatest rate of traffic fatalities per 10,000 vehicles and the highest rate of traffic accidents overall, one might be inclined to think that the level of awareness about traffic accident causes among Nigerians is very low. Instead, Asalor (2010) demonstrated that "Nigerians know quite a bit about what could cause road traffic accidents" and compared the predicament to "in the midst of plenty, there could be hunger." Ayodeji (2018) argues that there is an extensive amount of literature on traffic accidents, covering injuries, fatalities, and other relevant cause factors. However, Nigeria has had an extensive record of working to prevent traffic accidents. Sumaila (2013) revealed how the lead agency Federal Road Safety Commission (FRSC) was established to reduce road crashes, with the main objective of ensuring road safety. Since the first traffic accident in the year 1906, road safety has gotten a lot of attention, particularly from those in academia. Burn (2012) stressed that the condition of Nigerian roads was the main cause of road traffic crashes. Meanwhile, it was discovered that one of the major causes of traffic accidents in the nation where human error or behavioral change.

According to Shyngle (1978), cited by Ayodeji (2018), the country's high prevalence of RTAs was caused by the oil boom, which also triggered an increase in vehicle ownership. Furthermore, several research (Adebayo, 2015; Adogu, Ilika, & Asuzu, 2009; Bekibele et al., 2007; Nwadiaro, Ekwe, Akpayak, & Shitta, 2011; Sumaila, 2013) has linked vision impairment, low road safety compliance, and a high degree of illiteracy as key variables causing road accidents in Nigeria.

2.1.2 The Use of GIS in Hotspot Analysis

According to ESRI (2006), a geographic information system (GIS) is a computer system for collecting, storing, retrieving, analyzing, and displaying geographic data. The fundamental component of a GIS is the use of the notion of location as the foundation for structuring information systems. GIS represents a new paradigm for the organization of information and the creation of information systems. Analyzing traffic accidents include looking into their causes, identifying risky areas (accident-prone areas), deciding whether to improve road characteristics, and assessing traffic safety and improvement. Using techniques like linear referencing, dynamic segmentation, and spatial analysis, GIS can easily depict accident and traffic accident-based outcomes (Deepthi and Ganeshkumar 2010). Furthermore, the query execution is made simpler by graphical depiction. To improve highway safety analysis, road features, demographic, and socioeconomic data can also be incorporated (Kamalasudhan, 2011). Statistical mapping methods, such as K-means and the Moran I Incremental Spatial Autocorrelation Method (Abdulhafedh, 2017; Soltani, and Askari, 2017), can be used to map the spatial clustering of hotspots in point forms. Getis Ord Gi statistics can be found in Achu, Aju, Suresh, Manoharan, and Reghunath's (2019) paper as well as in Bassan's 2013 work and in Colak, Memisoglu, Erbas, and Bediroglu's (2018) work.

2.1.3 Hotspot Mapping and Heat Map

The significance of accident sites goes beyond their physical characteristics to encompass the broader environmental context in which accidents occur. An accident hotspot is a location where accidents are particularly frequent, to the extent that their recurrence can be reliably anticipated, typically over a one-year timeframe (Sherman, 1995). It's important to note that a hotspot is more often associated with accidents that happen on road transport. Different cluster analysis methods have been developed and can be generally classed when mapping these hotspots. Locating the areas where the accident occurrence is most concentrated and designating those places as "hot spots" is one of the most natural ways to cluster data.

On the other hand, the geographic entity's concentration at a particular spot is referred to as the "heat" in this context. Data are graphically represented in heat maps using color-coded techniques. Heat maps are primarily used to better represent the volume of events and locations within a dataset and to help guide users to the parts of data visualizations that matter most. Heat maps can be used in a wide variety of ways and are quite effective at highlighting trends. They naturally stand to reason: the greater the amount, the darker the shade (the higher the value, the closer the dispersion). Heat maps significantly improve the ability of existing data visualizations to quickly convey critical data insights to the user (Vasileva et al., 2018). In order to identify patterns of greater than average occurrence of events, such as traffic accidents, crime incidence, and activity in a location, heat mapping is a geographic method of visualization (Hooge and De, 2016). By interpolating discrete points to generate a continuous point surface, known as a density surface, heat maps can be produced.

According to McLafferty et al., (2000), a heat map is a hotspot surface map that looks like a temperature map from the weather report. The map depicts the accident intensity's kernel density surface map. Based on the locations of discrete events that are known, this technique entails calculating the density of accidents within a two-dimensional study area (Sha and Xie, 2016).

2.2 Empirical Review

Erdogan, Ilci, Soysal and Korkmaz (2015) examined traffic accident hotspots on the Turkish highway road network, by comparing the traditional hot spot detection methods with the spatial statistical methods. In the study it was discovered that the spatial methods were susceptible to accidents that occurred involving multiple vehicles. In another separate study, Erdogan, Yilmaz, Baybura, and Gullu (2008) employed statistical analysis and a geographic information system (GIS) as a management system for accident analysis to identify accident hotspots in Turkey's Afyonkarahisar administrative boundary. It was discovered that traffic agencies could access, process, and display accident data in a properly configured GIS system.

However, Olusina and Ajanaku (2017) examined different factors that cause road crashes within the Lagos Metropolis, where both primary and secondary data were used to map accident hotspots. Their study showed that the weighted severity index and KDE methods were used to calculate the accident location severity and vulnerability. It was discovered that road crashes were not usually as a result of bad road by the smoothness of such highway. While, Verma and Khan (2018) used the weighted severity measure in their study to identify location along Sagar and Shahgarh districts that were more prone to accidents. The cluster analysis was carried out using spatial autocorrelation to determine the hotspot distribution degree.

Ayodeji (2019) examined the geographic distribution of RTA severity in Nigeria, obtaining data from the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC). The study investigated historical data on traffic accidents using the exponential smoothing technique. In order to quantify spatial autocorrelation, global and local spatial association markers were created using the geographic information system. It was discovered that states in the northeast and northwest of Nigeria have major clusters of high, severe RTA.

Folorunso, Alayaki, Abiola, Easa, and Afolayan (2022) evaluate the accident hot spot using the geographic information systems (GIS) and spatial analysis along the Lokoja-Abuja-Kaduna highway in Nigeria. The study used a five-year period of accident data from 2013 to 2017. The study employed the mean center analysis and kernel density estimate method. With a significance level of 95–99%, the study discovered hotspots in the study area for the years 2013, 2014, and 2017 in particular. The results further revealed that hotspot sites are located with a high degree of accuracy in geometrically defined regions.

Aldala'in, Sukar, Obaidat, and Abd Manan (2023) examined the relationship between geometric design factors and criteria for traffic accidents based on accident hotspots on Jordan's Desert Highway. The data used for the study were sourced from the Jordan Traffic Department for the period of 2016 to 2019. While a topographic survey was carried out to investigate the road alignment and intersections at hotspot sites, the pattern of hotspots was identified using the GIS program Getis-Ord Gi. The study discovered that they were 80 accident hotspots along the study route, and further revealed that alignment has a significant impact on where traffic accident hotspots are located.

From most of the literatures reviewed on this study it was revealed that there are a number of studies conducted on road traffic crashes and hotspots globally and Nigeria in particular. Thus, identifying the location of the accident hotspots along Gadar Kafin Gana-Birnin Kudu expressway in Jigawa State has become very imperative. To the best of the researchers' knowledge, no such study has been conducted along this corridor. This is the gap this study intends to fill.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Study Area

The study route is a Federal Government-owned Kano/Kari road, which is a Trunk A237 route, that is about 21.3 km along the border between Jigawa and Kano states and is located between latitudes $11^{\circ}27'N$ - $11^{\circ}33'N$ and $9^{\circ}21'E$ - $9^{\circ}28'E$. The road started in Kwanar Huguma town in the Takai local government area of Kano state and proceeded through Kantoga, Bigidan, and the Birnin Kudu town in the Birnin Kudu local government of Jigawa State before arriving at Kafin Gana.

Figure 1: Kura Community
Source: Google Earth Image

3.2 Sources of Data

The study used both primary and secondary sources of data. The Global Positioning Systems (GPS) is one of the primary sources of data was used in the study. Google Earth 1 meter spatial resolution was then used to extract the route. On the other hand, the secondary data was obtained from the Federal Road Safety Commission, State Sector and Vehicle Inspection Officer office Dutse Command-Jigawa State-Nigeria.

3.3 Data Processing

a) Vector Data Creation (Road Map)

The Google Earth interface covering the study area was imported in the ArcGIS 10.1 environment using the Arc2 Earth extension tool. Features such as the study route, junctions, U-turn, intersecting roads were digitized using the Editor.

b) Creation of Database

All vector data (i.e. line and point features) were arranged in separate attribute tables. Here the road was labeled with its name. Similarly the accident location attribute table contains the records from the federal road safety commission. The coordinates and their attributes were entered into the Microsoft excel and then saved as Comma Separated Values CSV (comma delimited) format and imported into the ArcGIS 10.0 environment. The x and y coordinates define the position of an accident location on the map as a point feature and each point has its own attributes. The database is necessary in this study so that analysis can be performed on the data. The flow chart for data processing is represented in Fig.2

Figure 2: Flow Chart for Data Processing
Source: Adopted from Liang, Ma'seom and Hua (2005)

3.4 Methods of Data Analysis

3.4.1 Analysis on Causes of Accident

The Federal Road Safety Corps data stored in the database and a simple query statement (SQL) was used to visualize the causes of accidents from the record of FRSC and the results were summarized on maps, charts and tables.

3.4.2 Hotspot Analysis

The Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) in ArcGIS 10.1 was utilized in mapping the accident hotspots along the route. The KDE provides an estimate of the proportion of total accidents that can be expected to occur in any given map location. It works by first overlaying an area of interest with a fine rectangular grid. It then calculates an estimate of the density of accident in each grid cell which is based on a weight function - the kernel. The kernel is a function of specified shape and bandwidth (or search radius). The Kernel Density Estimation is given by the equation below (Deepthi and Ganeshkumar, 2010):

$$F(x,y) = 1/nh^2 \sum_{i=1} k\left(\frac{d_t}{h}\right) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where f is the density estimate at location (x, y) , h is the search radius (bandwidth or kernel size), n is numbers of observations (total number of accidents), K is the kernel function and, is the distance between the location (event point) (x,y) and location of the i^{th} observation. The mean and standard deviation of the Kernel Density Estimation was used to determine the hotspot and also a raster map was generated, where the intensity of traffic accidents is represented by continuous surfaces. Lighter shades were used

3.4.3 Ranking of Accident Hotspots

The Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) was used to weigh the severity of the accident (fatal, severe, and minor), and the Accident Point Weighting (APW) was calculated using the formula below.

$$APW = X_1W_1 + X_2W_2 + X_3W_3 \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where X_1 , X_2 and X_3 are the expected number of fatal, severe and minor injuries W_1 , W_2 and W_3 are the weightage of fatal, severe and minor injuries respectively (Troung and Sekhar, 2011).

Table 1: Weightages of types of Accidents

	Fatal	Serious Injury	Minor Injury	Weight (W_1)
Fatal	1	5	9	0.7
Serious Injury	1/5	1	9	0.25
Minor Injury	1/9	1/9	1	0.05

Source: Adopted Jobin (2015)

3.4.4 Estimation Techniques

In order to achieve the set objectives, a trend analysis of the accident casualty was conducted. On the other hand, the Global Positioning System (GPS) was employed to analyze and identify all the accident hotspot along the study route.

4.0 Result and Discussion

In this section of the study, the road traffic accident trend on the Gadar Kafin Gana to Birnin Kudu Highway from 2010-2023 was analyzed. Furthermore, the hotspots (risk sites) along the route were identified and mapped out using the Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) while the Accident Point Weighting (APW) was also used to rank the hotspots in terms of severity. After the hotspots were identified, the characteristics of the road and the roadside of the RTA hotspots were studied to determine their combined contribution.

4.1 Distribution of Accidents and Casualties along the Study Route

In the study route, there were 156 accident cases reported between 2010 and 2022 with 426 people involved, resulting in 177 fatalities and 249 injuries, according to FRSC and police records from Jigawa state. The distribution of road accidents and casualties along the study route is shown in table 2 below.

Table 2: Road Traffic Accident and Casualties in Gadar Kafin Gana to Birnin Kudu Expressway

Year	Number of Cases	Fatal		Serious Injury		Minor Injury		Total Person Involved	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
2010	9	10	34.5	7	24.1	12	41.4	29	100
2011	16	21	36.8	11	19.3	25	43.9	57	100
2012	20	32	40.0	12	15.0	36	45.0	80	100
2013	25	35	58.3	11	18.3	14	23.3	60	100
2014	17	24	45.3	4	7.5	25	47.2	53	100
2015	14	15	35.7	8	19.0	19	45.2	42	100

2016	10	3	27.3	2	18.2	6	54.5	11	100
2017	9	4	33.3	1	8.3	7	58.3	12	100
2018	11	5	23.8	6	28.6	10	47.6	21	100
2019	7	7	46.7	3	20.0	5	33.3	15	100
2020	8	8	47.1	4	23.5	5	29.4	17	100
2021	4	7	43.8	5	31.3	4	25.0	16	100
2022	9	6	46.2	3	23.1	4	30.8	13	100

Source: FRSC and Police Report (2023) from Jigawa State

An injury that typically results in death within a year, either directly or as a result of complications is referred to as a fatal accident, and the frequency and proportions of these accidents are shown in the table above. The study revealed that the highest fatal accident frequency was recorded in 2013 with 35 (58.3%). This is closely followed by 8 (47.1%), 7 (46.7%), and 9 (46.2%) fatal accidents that were reported in 2020, 2019, and 2022, respectively. The lowest number of fatal accidents which was 5 (23.8%) was reported in 2018, followed by 3 (27.3%) in 2016. With regards to serious injuries (which are injuries requiring medical interventions, either inside or outside of the hospital). The study found that the highest frequency of serious injuries recorded was 5 (31.3%) in 2021, followed by 6 (28.5%) injuries that occurred in 2018. Thus, the lowest frequency of serious injuries was observed in 2014, when there were 4 (7.5%), followed by 1 (8.3%) in 2017. An intensive study of the frequencies and percentages of minor injuries (defined as any injury resulting from a motor vehicle accident, including minor injuries and bruises, as well as hospitalization lasting less than 24 hours). The study further discovered that 2017, with 7 (58.3%) had the highest prevalence of minor injuries. In 2016, 6 (54.5%) minor injuries were sustained as a result. The frequency that was reported with the lowest minor injuries was 4 (25%) in 2021, followed by 5 (29.4%) in 2020.

Figure 3: Casualty trend along the study route 2010-2022

The reason for the drop in fatality during this year is not unconnected with the serious activities of the Federal Road Safety Corp and Vehicle Inspection Officer of Jigawa state along the route. The assertion that there is a decline in the number of road accidents on this route is true. However, the study discovered that deaths resulting from traffic accidents along the study route are on the increase from the casualty trend analysis depicted in figure 3 above, even though there is a decrease in the number of reported cases in this route within the study period in accordance with Bobai and Abarshi (2014).

4.2 Road Traffic Accidents Frequency and Hotspot Spatial Distribution along the Study Route

In this section, we look at how often road traffic accidents happen and how many people get hurt on the study route. Employing a mobile GPS receiver device, the coordinates of each accident scene along the research route from 2010 to 2022 were gathered, and the frequency of the accidents' occurrence was projected into a road map. The spatial pattern of traffic accidents along the Gadar Kafin Gana to Birnin Kudu Highway from 2010 to 2023 is depicted in Figure 4 and 5 below. As more crashes seem to occur frequently at particular flashpoints, such as where there are sharp bends, steep slopes, U-turns, markets and bad parts of the road, this demonstrates that the concentration of the accidents is not evenly distributed along the route.

However, the kernel density estimation's findings revealed seventeen (17) different hotspot locations. From figure 4 below it shows that the Kafin Gana Bridge at the starting point of this study is too narrow to safely fit more than two vehicles which is one of the locations marked with a red dot because it was considered to have a high rate of accident severity along the route.

Figure 4: Accident Hotspot location along the study route

Source: Author's analysis 2023

Figure 5: Severity of Hotspots along the study route
Source: Author’s analysis 2023

Nevertheless, it is clear that a narrow bridge would potentially have a high number of traffic accidents. Fortunately, drivers are more cautious on the bridge than at KM 1.6 which has a T-junction at Tsamiyar Tannaga, where there are many parked vehicles, some of which are loading and offloading cargo, and pedestrians who are crossing the road run the risk of being run over by approaching vehicles. Then, around KM 5.6, there is a Kantoga village with a very sharp bend, on market days, it is common to see pedestrians cross the road, making it possible for a car traveling too fast to easily hit and kill someone there. At KM 10.5 is the village of Bigidan, which has a sharp bend and some potholes in the road that force drivers traveling at high speeds to change lanes and risk colliding with other vehicles or losing control.

Additionally, KM 11.3 completes a double curve that is close to Alu Agro farms. Kwanar Mutuwa, from KM15.2 to Km15.7 and is a double sharp bend with significant potholes that caused many crashes along the study route and resulted to the mass burial of some accident victims who had previously been dead and reduced to ashes. Another sharp bend can be found at KM18.5 in front of a KEDCO power office, and the final bend in Birnin Kudu town is another bend with a slope and potholes. These two bends are accident hotspots because they are frequently used by pedestrians heading to the nearby health center.

Its shown on the maps from the study that the hotspots with higher density are regular at points where there are settlements, intersecting road, sharp bend and river crossing the road indicating places with bridges. Figure 6 shows the frequencies of road accident at the hotspots along the route.

Figure 6: Hotspots and Accident frequency along the route from 2010-2022

Source: Author’s Analysis, 2023

The results of the thirteen-year study showed that Kantoga, with 50 recorded cases, has the highest number of accidents, followed by Alu Agro Farm, with 37 cases. Other accident-prone areas include Gana Bridge, the KEDCO Power Office, Kwanar Mutuwa KM 15.2 and KM15.9 Birnin Kudu Town, each had 30, 28, 28 and 27 cases respectively been reported. The study also found that some of these places have a high accident rate because reckless drivers frequently go at fast speeds through small settlements or around steep curves, hitting people who are crossing the road carelessly or petty business owners.

4.3 Ranking of Road Traffic Accident Hotspots in the Study Area

To rank accident hotspots, the Accident Point Weightage (APW) formula was used. The weighting method made use of Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) coefficients for each type of accident. However, it was multiplied by 0.7 for a fatal accident, 0.25 for a major injury, and 0.05 for a minor injury. Data on the frequency of traffic accidents on the Gadar Kafin Gana to Birnin Kudu Expressway were examined in order to assess the accident hotspot area. A road section considered to be particularly prone to vehicular crashes is known as a hotspot, according to Kowtanapanich (2006). Table 2 lists the order of accidents along the route as determined by APW. Kantoga village which is located along the research route was discovered to have the highest Accident Point Weighting, with a value of 16.95, according to the table below.

Table 2: Ranking of the Hotspots along the study route

S/N	Location	fatal (X ₁)	Serious (X ₂)	Minor (X ₃)	Total	APW	RANKING
1	KM 5.6 Kantoga	21	4	25	50	16.95	1
2	KM 13 Alu Agro Farm	20	4	13	37	15.45	2
3	Kafin Gana Bridge	15	3	12	30	11.85	3
4	KM 18.6 KEDCO Power Office	15	3	10	28	11.75	4
5	KM 15.2 Kwanar Mutuwa I	14	6	8	28	11.7	5
6	KM 15.9 Kwanar Mutuwa II	13	3	11	27	10.4	6

7	KM 20 Birnin Kudu Town	13	2	9	24	10.05	7
8	KM 10.5 Bigidan	10	6	13	29	9.15	8
9	KM 1.6 Tsamiyar	8	6	10	24	7.6	9
10	KM 2.6 Kafin Gana Town	6	10	15	31	7.45	10
11	KM 11.3	16	1	9	26	7	11
12	KM 14.8	7	3	6	16	5.95	12
13	KM 6.9	6	4	10	20	5.7	13
14	KM 4.2	5	5	8	18	5.15	14
15	KM 21.3	4	3	4	11	3.75	15
16	KM 17.3	2	7	3	12	3.3	16
17	KM 2.4	2	7	6	15	3.15	17

Source: Author’s Analysis, 2023

Alu Agro Farm came in second place, scoring 15.45, while Kafin Gana Bridge came in third, scoring 11.85. With an APW rating of 10.05, 9.15, 7.6 and 7.45, respectively, Birnin Kudu town, Bigidan, Tsamiyar and Kafin Gana town were placed as the 7th, 8th, 9th and 10th towns. In terms of fatal accidents, KM 21.3, 17.3, and 2.4 came in 15th, 16th, and 17th place, respectively. The locations along this route with the most accidents also happen to have the highest Accident Point Weightage. More concerning is the fact that although the study route is only 21.3 kilometers long, it contains seventeen accident hotspots where several travelers have lost their lives and many of these incidents have gone unreported. Because of the multiple accident hotspots along this route, emergency response teams are required to be stationed there. As reaffirm by Osayomi and Areola (2015) that emphasis on the significance of providing immediate aid in locations with a higher accident risk. Plate 1 below shows some selected accident hotspot along the study route.

Narrow Bridge in Gadar Kafin Gana

Pedestrian crossing road in Kafin Gana

Accident Scene at 13.0 KM Sharp Curve

Pot Hole at 15.7 KM at a sharp bend

Plate 1: Showing different accident spot on the study route

In the community of Gadar Kafin Ghana, plate 1 depicts a narrowed bridge that can only accommodate two vehicles at once. When an accident occurs, it happens with a lot of congestion at KM 13 Kwanar Mutuwa, a dangerous turn with very deep potholes located at KM 15.7. The main findings of this study were that the concentration of the accident hotspot is not fairly distributed along the route, as more incidents seem to occur in some flashpoints, such as where there are sharp bends, slopes, U-turns, built-up intersections, bridges, and potholes of the study route. Thus, it is interesting to note that the findings of this study are in line with those of Lee & Fred (1999) and Jobin (2015), who discovered that road features, roadside characteristics, and road design, among other things, are the main contributing variables to road traffic accidents globally.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

In addition to the high number of deaths and injuries they cause, traffic accidents are a serious social and economic issue globally. The study route's traffic accident and fatality trend were investigated, and Kernel Density Estimation was used to map the study area's accident hotspots. While the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Accident Point Weighting (APW) formulas were used to rank areas in the study geographic area with a high concentration of traffic accidents. Interestingly, it is possible to greatly increase road safety by identifying accident hotspots and the factors that influence them as conducted by this study. Consequently, the following recommendations were made:

- i. The use of geographic information system (GIS) as a vital tool of identifying and analyzing spatial distribution pattern of accident hotspot that can help engineers and traffic managers to reduce the possibility of accident occurring. Furthermore, planners, traffic managers, engineers, and scholars can easily use it to identify variables that affect locations' safety and classify it as dangerous spot.
- ii. Due to the large number of accident hotspots along this route. It is crucial that the FRSC, VIO, and Police in Jigawa state to focus their manpower and resources on the hotspots revealed by this study. This will have a significant impact on lowering traffic accidents in the study area.
- iii. The road infrastructure, which includes key components like bridges and road signs, needs to undergo thorough maintenance. This will ensure complete road safety and convenience for all users, whenever any poor sections of the road with potholes, missing road signs and pedestrian bridges are installed right away.
- iv. Road users' increased awareness of the dangers of driving at high speeds on routes with sharp bends, narrow bridges, and potholes, will go a long way toward promoting good traffic rule compliance.

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